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Abstract: This deliverable provides guidelines for ethics considerations in making biomedical survey data FAIR, considering the specific setting of a survey data collection and the fact that biomedical data are a special category of personal data (data concerning health as defined in the General Data Protection regulation, GDPR) that require special protection when made accessible and re-usable.

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Executive Summary

This report is Deliverable 5.1 of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, and a result of Task 1 focusing on the legal, ethical, and technological issues of access to biomedical data. The aim of the task is to make biomedical data available to the research community via data access that follows the FAIR principles.

Measuring health and its associations with indicators of socio-economic status are important objectives for population-based (social) surveys. While self-reported health measures carry important information, they need to be supplemented by objective health measures to distinguish, as much as possible, the objective health status from the respondent's subjective perception of this status. Two salient examples may illustrate this point. Data derived from dried blood spot samples which allow a better evaluation of the risk of cardiovascular diseases and cognitive decline than self-reports. Objective physical activity data collected through accelerometers allow capturing vital determinants for old age mobility and health such as activity levels, sleep patterns and sedentary behaviour better than a self-report of daily activities that may be wishfully biased.

In connection with this development and in particular in relation to the question of how these new data can be made accessible to researchers, questions related to ethics considerations and the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (FAIR) had to be addressed. This deliverable therefore provides general guidelines for ethics considerations in making such objective health data FAIR, based on the experiences made in Wave 6 of the *Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe* (SHARE) when the collection of objective health data alongside regular survey data in the form of dried blood samples was introduced. This development was continued in SHARE Wave 8 with the introduction of accelerometer data.

This deliverable first addresses ethical considerations. For instance, the principle to not harm survey participants needs an extension when collecting biomarker data in surveys – this means that avoiding harm besides avoiding violation of confidentiality and resultant consequences needs to include avoidance of physical harm such as temporary discomfort or pain. Similarly, the concepts of informed consent and protection of anonymity and confidentiality demand an adequate adaption to suit the collection of objective health data in survey settings. To ensure the appropriateness of the practical implementation of the ethics standards and principles as well as data protection measures within a research project a review by a competent ethics committee can be helpful (and therefore is recommended) in many cases when collecting objective health data in the context of a survey – and in some cases, such as the inclusion of a blood sample collection, is legally required by law (in many countries).

Moreover, this deliverable explains the general requirements and considerations of the FAIR principles, according to which all research data needs to be "Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable". In this

connection the compliance of SHARE data, including the biomarker and accelerometer data, with the FAIR principles is examined and clarified in an exemplary manner.

Findability is ensured through all data being permanently identifiable and locatable through DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) and registration in a repository that also contains metadata, a collection of bibliographical and content information, referring to the registered dataset. *Access* to SHARE data is provided free of charge to the scientific community after registration in accordance with clearly defined Conditions of Use. Furthermore, access to the data is subject European Union as well as national data protection provisions. The evaluation of special requirements regarding access to sensitive health data has been taken into consideration. The interdisciplinary *interoperability* of SHARE data is ensured by its availability for a variety of statistical software and its comprehensive documentation. *Re-usability* is ensured through several measures such as archiving of the SHARE data with a detailed documentation of the (meta)data, the publication of data quality assurance processes or the provision of generated modules and datasets.

In summary, this deliverable provides guidelines for making biomedical survey data satisfy recognised ethical standards, as well as ensuring such data are FAIR, in particular, by using SHARE and its new objective health data as an example.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

da ra	Data registration agency for social science and economic data
DBS	Dried blood spots
DBSS	Dried blood spot samples
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
MPG	Max Planck Society
SHARE	The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
VBS	Venous Blood Spots
WP(#)	Work Package(number) of the SSHOC project

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	7
2. Biomarker and accelerometer data in SHARE	8
3. Ethics considerations	10
3.1 'Do no harm'	10
3.2 Informed consent	10
3.3 Protection of anonymity and confidentiality	11
3.4 Ethical review	12
4. Compliance with the FAIR principles	14
4.1 Findability	14
4.2 Accessibility	16
4.3 Interoperability	17
4.4 Re-usability	18
5. Conclusion	20
References	22

1. Introduction

Technological development continues to offer new ways of health data collection that go beyond asking survey questions such as the collection of biological samples for later laboratory analyses and tracking people's behaviour, health or movements. These objective measures overcome certain shortcomings of self-reported health measures, and integrating them into survey research allows an in-depth analysis of health and potential influencing factors (cf. McDade et al., 2007, p. 901ff.). Including such data in social survey databases involves new methods of data collection for survey researchers. Introducing such new methods of data collection, however, may amplify the ethics issues that need to be addressed and extend the requirements for researchers in relation to legal provisions (cf. Schmidutz, 2018, p. 4). Therefore, the already applied measures to ensure compliance with ethics standards and data protection requirements have to be reconsidered when including such innovative variables in social survey databases.

Furthermore, researchers and data archives have to take into account the intrinsic differences of such data collections in comparison to traditional self-reported survey data when aiming at making them available to the scientific community for research purposes. These data must often be extensively processed, validated and calibrated before they can be made accessible and subsequently analysed with the statistical techniques and models that are common in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). While survey data usually is available directly after the data collection, the inclusion of biological samples into the database requires an additional step: the analyses of the samples (cf. Schmidutz, 2019, p. 8). Other types of innovative data collection, such as accelerometer data (i.e. physical activity data that is collected by using accelerometry, a technique for quantifying movement patterns), are very large in size. This makes it difficult for individual researchers to handle them, and therefore gives rise to the question if they can only or should additionally be released in an aggregated form to the scientific community. These different underlying conditions demand new ways of providing access to the data and require researchers and data archives to consider if new data protection rules and access policies are needed when making such new types of data available for scientific research.

The *Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe* (SHARE)¹, currently works on the development of a strategy to provide access to such data in combination with the already established access to the traditional self-reported data collected in the SHARE project. In this connection, the focus lies on the inclusion of two different types of innovative data in the released SHARE database: objective health data

¹ The *Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe* (SHARE) is a multidisciplinary and cross-national panel study that incorporates information regarding social, economic and health factors of more than 140,000 individuals from 27 European countries and Israel aged 50 or older as well as national institutional and social policy conditions. For more information, see the website of the SHARE project: <http://www.share-eric.eu/>.

derived from dried blood spot (DBS) samples and accelerometer data. When developing this strategy, the question has been raised, if granting access to scientific researchers to such data in combination with the traditional self-reported data of a large international social survey in general will give rise to specific ethics issues that need to be addressed. This question, in particular, seems to be of relevance with regard to the aim of providing access to data to the scientific community in compliance with the FAIR principles.

The FAIR principles are key for establishing open science as good scientific practice in the research community. SSHOC therefore provides many tools for the Social Sciences and Humanities to establish FAIR principles throughout the research process and enable researchers to apply the FAIR principles and open science practices in their own work. This deliverable therefore is targeted at researchers who consider the collection of objective health data or biomedical data in a survey setting. According to the FAIR principles, research data shall be "findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable". Therefore, this deliverable will address the question how these requirements can be met in such a setting and if the inclusion of biomarker or accelerometer data in a social survey database will make it necessary to reconsider and adapt certain measures regarding the access to the database and the provision of related documentation and metadata.

2. Biomarker and accelerometer data in SHARE

In the sixth data collection wave of SHARE, DBS samples have been collected as part of the regular SHARE interview in most of the countries that participated in the study.² To enhance objective information about health, blood of the participants in SHARE has been collected by trained SHARE interviewers in form of DBS samples. Prior to the DBS collection, respondents' informed consent was obtained in a written form (cf. Schmidutz & Weiss, 2017, p. 170). The collection of dried blood spots is a minimally invasive and comparatively painless procedure suitable for nonclinical settings (cf. McDade et al., 2007, p. 907). Many blood markers can be analysed from this material, which may signal the risk of cardiovascular diseases and cognitive decline. Such health data are defined as a special category of personal data in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and therefore require special protection. Furthermore, ethics considerations might be raised when making them accessible and re-usable.

² More details regarding the participating countries, including a documentation of the central legal requirements and ethical issues related to the collection of DBS samples in each country are provided in Schmidutz (2018). For a more general description of the implementation, conduction, and results of the DBS collection, see M. Börsch-Supan et al. (2020).

Besides the necessary analyses of the DBS samples, it has to be taken into account that the samples gained in a survey are collected in the field and not in a controlled medical setting.³ Therefore, environmental conditions and impact of handling during blood taking and transport to the biobank have to be considered and validated with venous blood samples and epidemiological data. Such processing of the samples and the data retrieved from the samples needs to be documented in an adequate manner and the documentation has to be provided together with the data to users (cf. A. Börsch-Supan et al., forthcoming). Only in the light of such metadata, the results of scientific analyses of the DBS data can be interpreted in an adequate manner.

In addition to the enhancement of the SHARE survey data with DBS data, SHARE will extend the regular survey with the collection of objective physical activity data by using accelerometry. The accelerometer measures can reliably capture activity levels, sleep patterns and sedentary behaviour, which are currently considered major determinants of health and mobility in old age. Accelerometers generate a large volume of acceleration signal data, which in comparison to the traditional self-reported data entail additional logistical (storage, transmission, handling) and analytic challenges for survey researchers. Targeted algorithms and sufficient computational space are needed for processing raw accelerometer data and deriving aggregated variables cf. Milestone 22 of SSHOC). Against this background, SHARE is working on the implementation of a dedicated access plan to the accelerometer data in compliance with the FAIR principles (see D5.3 of SSHOC, forthcoming). In particular, the aggregation of the data has to be documented and the documentation has to be provided together with the aggregated data to researchers in the form of metadata, whenever direct access provision to the raw data is not possible.

³ Hence, SHARE data cannot be used to infer a medical diagnosis of any single respondent.

3. Ethics considerations

At its core, research ethics seek to protect the interests and well-being of research participants (cf. National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979). They are guided by the core principles of 'do not harm', informed consent, protection of anonymity and confidentiality (cf. Schmidutz et al., 2013, p. 10). With regard to the enhancement of survey data with objective health data, such as the biomarker and accelerometer data, most of these ethics principles have to be considered during the phases of data collection and data processing before the actual analyses of the data can take place.

'Do no harm'

The principle of 'do no harm' needs particular attention before and during the collection of the data but also during subsequent data processing. It requires researchers to conduct their research in a way that minimises the potential of social harm to certain groups as well as ensures the well-being of research subjects (cf. Dench et al., 2004, p. 17 & 56). The participation in research projects should not lead to any disadvantages for respondents (cf. RESPECT, 2004). In social science research, it can be argued that the most severe risk of harm for respondents is the violation of confidentiality and consequences that may follow from such a violation (cf. Singer, 2008, p. 90). However, in the context of DBS, physical harm such as temporary discomfort or pain has to be considered as well.

When collecting DBS samples in the context of a survey by trained interviewers, this also means that additional measures have to be taken such as the instruction of interviewers on how to take the DBS samples without harming the respondents and procedures have to be in place to ensure that interviewers follow the instructions when carrying out the blood collection. Similarly, when collecting accelerometer data, it has to be ensured that the accelerometer devices and the handling of the devices do not pose risks for the health of the persons participating in this data collection.

In Wave 6 of the SHARE data collection, e.g., interviewers who were supposed to collect DBS were trained in depth in taking the samples as well as for possible situations occurring during the DBS collection. This training took half a day and consisted of an introduction of the theoretical background, a demonstration of the material, a mock interview, a hands-on training with certification and a question-and-answer session. Additionally, an instruction manual was used, which included step-by-step instructions and a short video demonstrating the collection of DBS, the handling of the DBS card on-site, its shipment, arrival and handling at the SHARE Biobank (cf. Schmidutz & Weiss, 2017, p. 173).

Informed consent

Voluntary informed consent is another essential prerequisite for conducting research in an ethical manner. In order to obtain informed consent, researchers need to provide sufficient information on the

research project and its purpose to the participants so that participants can come to a well-informed decision (cf. Singer, 2008, p. 85). This information should include details on the purposes of the study, the study procedures, benefits as well as potential risks, and their rights (cf. Shahnazarian et al., p. 3). Further, participants must be given the possibility to refuse to participate as well as withdraw their consent without causing negative repercussions for themselves (cf. Crow et al., 2006, p. 83f.). All these requirements also hold true for parts of the study such as a collection of DBS and accelerometer data. Depending on the concrete study design one or several consent questions (including the provision of all relevant information) can be used with regard to different parts of the study.

In SHARE, e.g., in general, all respondents are volunteers, and the entire data collection is based on informed consent. Before starting the interview of each wave, each respondent's consent is obtained with regard to his/her participation. Additionally, during the interview answers to all questions are voluntary.

This also concerns respondents' participation in the accelerometer data collection. Regarding this part of the data collection, during the regular SHARE interview, the respondents are informed about the purpose of this specific part of the study first and then asked to participate in the accelerometer project. Respondents, who agreed to participate in the accelerometer project, subsequently are provided with an accelerometer device via postal mail accompanied with detailed instructions and information on the accelerometry study. They may refuse to participate at any time without any negative consequences or occurring costs (return shipment of the device is covered by SHARE).

Regarding the collection of DBS in SHARE Wave 6, furthermore, explicit separate informed consent was obtained from the participants in a written form prior to the sample collection in addition to the initial consent for participation in the SHARE study.

Protection of anonymity and confidentiality

In order to ensure conformity with the principles of protection of anonymity and confidentiality, also, adequate procedures and technical and organisational security measures have to be defined prior to the data collection and processing.

These measures and procedures, however, also are of relevance in relation to data access. In this connection, it is of particular importance to ensure compliance with the relevant legal provisions of data protection. Here, it has to be taken into account that biomarker data derived from DBS and accelerometer data, are data concerning health and therefore are defined as a special category of personal data in accordance with Article 9 (1) of the GDPR. These data require special protection when made accessible and re-usable. In order to protect the participants' anonymity and ensure the confidentiality of their data during the complete research process, special safeguards such as anonymisation and pseudo-anonymisation measures have to be implemented.

Since the SHARE data collection also includes the collection of self-reported health related data, the project, in general, places particular importance on the compliance with European and national data protection law as well as on the safeguarding of sensitive personal data and confidential information. All names and other personal information that could be used to identify individuals or households are removed from any data sets that are made available to researchers. In the same manner, adequate measures to ensure the safeguarding of sensitive personal data and confidential information are applied to accelerometer data and data derived from DBS.

Ethical review

In order to ensure the appropriateness of the practical implementation of the ethics standards and principles as well as data protection measures within a research project, review by a competent ethics committee is recommended. In some countries – and in particular with regard to research that includes the collection of human cells/tissues – there is a legal obligation to undergo ethics review.

Such a review by a competent ethics committee in the first place helps to reassure the responsible researchers that the procedures and measures taken in connection with the research project address the ethics issues related to the project in an appropriate manner. It, however, does not relieve the researchers from their responsibilities in this regard. I.e., first, prior to starting with projects that aim at the inclusion biological samples in social surveys, some basic reflections of ethics issues that may be of relevance in relation to the planned project and of the ethics standards in relation to the envisaged project are necessary. In this connection, it is of particular importance to take all perspectives of the involved parties (i.e., researchers, survey agencies, interviewers and participants) into account. Only on the basis of such reflections it will be possible to demonstrate compliance with ethics standards (Schmidutz 2018, p. 15). Second, adequate procedures have to be developed: from the consent procedures to the procedures related to the processing of the data and/or samples to the procedures for storage and analyses of the data and/or samples to any subsequent procedures regarding the processing, linkage and dissemination of the analyses data (Schmidutz 2018, p. 13). In this connection also consent and other fieldwork documents have to be prepared and an appropriate training for the interviewers has to be set up. All this needs to be documented in an appropriate manner and this documentation can finally be submitted to a competent ethics committee (together with a description, of the project including its rationale and purposes).

The SHARE project and its data collection procedures, e.g., are reviewed on a regular basis prior to each new wave of data collection. Most recently the SHARE data collection procedures have been reviewed and approved by the Ethics Council of the Max Planck Society (MPG). It carefully reviewed the material of the SHARE project and attested that the overall research project and its procedures, the measures to assure confidentiality and data privacy, and the information given to the participants agree with international ethical standards. SHARE-ERIC's activities related to human subjects' research are guided by international research ethics principles such as the Respect Code of Practice for Socio-Economic Research and the Declaration of Helsinki (as prepared by the Council for International Organizations of

Medical Sciences in collaboration with the World Health Organization, last revised at the 64th WMA Meeting held in Fortaleza/Brazil in October 2013). Moreover, all activities of SHARE related to human subjects research is guided by the Declaration of Helsinki and the International Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical Research involving Human Subjects.

The implementation of the accelerometry study has been approved along the regular SHARE approval since the accelerometry study is an integrated module in the SHARE questionnaire. The collection of DBS samples in SHARE Wave 6 has been approved additionally and separately by the concerned national ethics committees of all participating countries.⁴

⁴ The legal provisions as well as the requirements of ethical reviews of research projects vary extensively between the in SHARE participating countries. See Schmidutz (2016) for further information on policy-rules for the collection of biomarkers in social surveys and a detailed description of the experiences with regard to research ethics that have been made during the implementation process in SHARE.

4. Compliance with the FAIR principles

Besides the above-mentioned principles of research ethics, however, the stipulations of professional ethics and standards of good scientific practice have to be taken into account. This, in particular, concerns the responsibility of researchers to ensure the verifiability and reproducibility of the results of scientific analyses (cf. Max Planck Society, 2009). A detailed documentation of every methodological step of the research project is essential to allow scholars to verify their colleagues findings (cf. Diekmann, 2013, p. 83ff.). Therefore, it is of particular importance to ensure that all necessary metadata needed by researchers to comply with these requirements are made available to them in a comprehensible form when making data accessible and re-usable for scientific research.

As a guideline for good scientific practice, scientists as well as representatives of the industry, funding agencies and scholarly publishers have developed the FAIR Guiding Principles for the publication of digital resources (cf. Wilkinson et al., 2016; Wilkinson et al., 2018). Following these principles, research data shall be "findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable" to ensure scientific quality and to enhance knowledge and discovery (cf. Wilkinson et al., 2016). These guidelines go beyond a traditional understanding of data and therefore also apply to algorithms, tools or metadata (cf. Wilkinson et al., 2016). Due to the increasing employment of computational systems, the FAIR principles highlight the importance of machine actionability – meaning that data should be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable both to humans and computational systems (cf. Wilkinson et al., 2016). Hence, the usage of a "widely-accepted machine-readable framework" (Mons et al., 2017, p. 51) would be ideal. It is hoped that the implementation of the FAIR principles will lead to an improvement in data management and stewardship so that researchers can use existing data to its full potential and thereby thriving scientific innovation.

The FAIR Guidelines have rapidly gained popularity in bio- and natural sciences (cf. van Reisen et al., 2020). However, Mons et al. (2017) criticise that a large share of datasets are still unavailable for re-use. Aiming at providing access to biomarker and accelerometer data to the scientific community, it has to be reflected upon how the implementation of the FAIR principles can be achieved in this context while still adhering to the above mentioned ethical core principles. Here, computer and computer-assisted data administration and analysis will become highly relevant to facilitate the usage of such large-scale data (cf. Boeckhout et al., 2018, p. 932f.). To further promote this process of FAIR data stewardship, it requires the development of certain community specific policies that stipulate how the available resources will and should work (cf. Mons et al., 2017, p. 50).

4.1 Findability

In order to make data findable for both, humans and computer systems, data as well as associated metadata should be assigned an abiding, unique identifier and registered in a comprehensible resource (cf. Wilkinson et al., 2016), for example a data archive or institutional repository (cf. Boeckhout et al.,

2018, p. 932). In order to be able to find certain data it is of utmost importance that relevant metadata is available. To assist researchers and computational agents in finding and assessing relevant and appropriate data sets, metadata should always be clearly marked with the unique identifier of the data that it is describing and should go into detail about the context, characteristics and quality of the dataset (cf. Go Fair).

The growing number of databases hosting data has resulted in some confusion over where to store new data and where to find the most current one (cf. McQuilton et al., 2016, p. 2). Various data discovery platforms exist to improve the findability of biomedical data. Some platforms provide full data sets, others grant access to metadata that is linked to the original data source (cf. Trifan & Oliveira, 2019). One of the most important repositories for biomedical publications is PubMed which still lacks providing datasets (Deshpande et al., 2019). In addition to the increasing number of databases, there appears to be no consensus on data format standards or reporting guidelines (cf. McQuilton et al., 2016, p. 2). Across all scientific disciplines, thousands of standards have been developed and implemented by countless data repositories (cf. Sansone et al., 2019, p. 358). To address these obstacles, the portal FAIRsharing, formerly BioSharing, had been launched (cf. McQuilton et al., 2016, p. 2). FAIRsharing is a community-driven portal that provides information on data and metadata standards, linked to databases, repositories and data policies for various scientific disciplines (see: <https://fairsharing.org/>). In doing so, it "curates information on standards employed for the identification, citation and reporting of data and metadata" (Sansone et al., 2019, p. 359). However, the number of available databases at FAIRsharing shows that the platform is predominantly used by the natural sciences and the overall number of databases uploaded is small (less than 2000 at time of writing).

A platform predominantly used by the social sciences is the Harvard Dataverse (cf. Wilkinson et al., 2016, p. 5; see <https://support.dataverse.harvard.edu/>). It is a free repository where data and metadata can be shared with the scientific community, stored for future research and accessed by scientists from any fields of research. A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is automatically assigned to every published data set for citation purposes and findability (cf. Harvard Dataverse Support, 2020). Harvard Dataverse currently hosts almost 100.000 datasets (cf. Harvard Dataverse, 2020). Within the SSHOC task 5.2 "Hosting and sharing data repositories" the software will be adjusted to the needs of the European research infrastructures in the social sciences and humanities. The adaptation of Dataverse for the SSHOC community again is discipline-specific, however the integration into EOSC yields hope for interdisciplinary findability and outreach, also for datasets at the intersection of several disciplines.

Objective health data collected in surveys is at the intersection of social sciences and biomedical data. Therefore, in practice, it might be worth considering to list datasets containing biomarker and accelerometer data in several registries to reach the researchers of different fields most effectively. Uploading datasets to repositories such as FAIRsharing or the Harvard Dataverse supports the findability and accessibility of small datasets. Large datasets can be made findable by providing metadata at repositories.

To ensure findability, SHARE uses DOI's to make datasets permanently identifiable and locatable. This will also hold for the biomarker and accelerometer data collected within SHARE. SHARE data is registered in the repository of da|ra, which links every DOI to a set of metadata, a collection of bibliographical and content information, referring to the registered dataset (title, author, publication date, copyright etc.). Publishing elaborate metadata on the biological biomarkers and accelerometer data on a pertinent repository for biomedical data might contribute to the findability of the objective health measures SHARE provides, while still meeting the requirements of the GDPR.

4.2 Accessibility

The FAIR principles state that data should be accessible and retrievable by their identifier using "standardized communications protocol" (Wilkinson et al., 2016, p. 4). Data and metadata should be stored for the long term and access to metadata should still be available even when the data is not. Even though relevant stakeholders call for making biomedical data available to the scientific community, healthcare data is often not published due to privacy concerns, lack of integration or legal constraints (Deshpande et al., 2019). In the context of objective health data collected in surveys, some form of access limitation might be needed to protect the participants' privacy.

However, the principles take into account that certain data cannot be released via open access because of ethical or legal constraints but can still be FAIR by publishing informative metadata about the dataset and by including information on data access regulations (Wilkinson et al., 2018) as well as information on usage and publication conditions (Boeckhout et al., 2018). Further, scholars have developed the FAIR Health Principles, when dealing with health-related or sensitive personal data (Holub et al., 2018). To establish a balance between reproducibility and the participants' privacy, Holub et al. (2018) suggest to name the data controller, who is responsible for the biological material and data, as a contact person for research participants and authorities. Before providing access to sensitive data, intended research projects should be assessed with respect to their ethics approval as well as their adherence to informed consent. The FAIR Health Principles further state, that privacy-enhancing technologies should be applied to all personal data while maintaining full value of the data; remaining privacy risks should be considered. While the FAIR principles emphasize the importance of clarity and transparency regarding the access and usage conditions (cf. Mons et al., 2017), the FAIR-Health principles state the necessity of developing policies and guidelines for privacy respecting data storage and processing (cf. Holub et al., 2018).

In the case of SHARE, the data is made available to the scientific research community as soon as possible, i.e., after the data is cleaned and checked for data protection/GDPR related issues. Currently, access to the SHARE data is provided free of charge to the scientific community after a registration. The data is subject to national as well as European Union data protection laws and the publicly available Conditions of Use (see: SHARE-ERIC, 2020). If special requirements for providing access to the SHARE biomarker and accelerometer data are needed, this will be evaluated throughout the SSHOC project within Task 1 of WP5. Further developments will be reported in the respective data access protocols, published as Deliverable D5.2 for DBSS data and as D5.3 for accelerometer data.

4.3 Interoperability

Since different data often needs to be merged, datasets should be ready to be exchanged, interpreted and combined in a (semi)automated way by humans as well as computer systems. Therefore, to be interoperable, data as well as metadata should be described and structured in a "formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language" (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Using domain-specific standards in structuring data and formatting metadata would facilitate the mining and integration of different data sources (Borgman, 2012). In practice, metadata stored in repositories still feature certain quality issues such as inconsistency and incompleteness which makes it difficult to make sense of the metadata, thereby hindering interoperability and re-usability (cf. Hu et al., 2017, p. 1f.). Since FAIR metadata is seen as a crucial step towards FAIRness (cf. Mons et al., 2017, p. 54), any documentation on the data should be itself FAIR.

In some cases, granting access to the original biological material might not be fruitful nor feasible since the vast amount of data might not be usable by researchers or certain analytical programs (cf. Holub et al., 2018). Therefore, data processing and preparation need to take interoperability into account as well. To ensure interoperability of objective health data, additional actions need to be taken in comparison to traditional survey data. Objective health data must often be extensively processed, validated and calibrated before they can be made accessible and subsequently analysed with the statistical techniques and models that are common in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). While survey data usually is available directly after the data collection (after the necessary subsequent data cleaning and quality checks are carried out), the inclusion of biological samples into the database, e.g., requires an additional step: the analyses of the samples (cf. Schmidutz, 2019, p. 8). Only by means of the analyses the samples are converted into variables, so-called biomarkers (i.e., objective health data), which can be used in statistical analyses for research on, e.g., health and ageing. An overview of the derived biomarkers is documented in SSHOC project MS21 (*Protocol of laboratory processing of DBSS data*).

In order to ensure interoperability in SHARE, data is made available to the research community for two of the most common statistical software packages Stata and SPSS. However, users of other statistical software (e.g., R, SAS or Python) can access the data as well because conversion of datasets between statistical software packages is a standard procedure by now. For example, the open software application R supports packages to read-in Stata and SPSS files, which allow SHARE data to be analysed with open software as well. Within all these statistical software applications, SHARE data can be combined with other data sources, e.g. regional data, in any format the software supports. The standards and vocabularies used allow interdisciplinary interoperability. The SHARE (meta)data is comprehensively documented, to enable researchers from all disciplines to use it for their research and combine it with other datasets. The documentation complies with the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) standards, an international standard for the description and management of survey and observational data that allows machine actionability (cf. DDI Alliance, 2020). DDI standards are used in the social, economic as well as health sciences and therefore appear as a broadly applicable framework

suitable for SHARE. Metadata for biomarker and accelerometer data in SHARE will be documented along the regular SHARE data and will be made available in a similar manner in the SHARE Data and Documentation Tool, also strictly following DDI standards.

4.4 Re-usability

The re-usability of data is an important requirement for the replication and validation of previous research findings as well as for the promotion of scientific knowledge (cf. Deshpande et al., 2019). Even when a dataset is findable, accessible and interoperable, it still does not ensure that researchers will be able to re-use the data in the future. In order to be re-usable, scientists and computer systems have to be able to assess whether the data is appropriate for the attempted research (cf. Go Fair). Hence, the data and metadata has to be sufficiently well-described (cf. Wilkinson et al., 2016). Therefore, standards on how data and metadata should be reported are crucial for their re-usability and consequentially for scientific innovation and reproducibility (cf. Sansone et al., 2019, p. 364). To promote data sharing and their re-use, field-specific data and metadata standards as well as providing an incentive to comply with these would facilitate this process (cf. Boeckhout et al., 2018, p. 933). However, the re-use of available data poses the potential risks of incorrect conclusions, errors or bias because scholars might be less familiar with certain details and limitations of the original study (cf. Boeckhout et al., 2018, p. 934; Spertus, 2012, p. 143). Consequentially, transparency about (re)used data is necessary on the part of researchers and data stewardship that is adhering to the FAIR principles within the scientific community is of vital importance (cf. Boeckhout et al., 2018, p. 934). This concerns highlighting the importance of meaningful metadata.

To make data re-usable for other scientists, a good description of the data includes information on the original purpose of the generated/collected data, methodological issues as well as ensuring that all variables are adequately named (cf. Go Fair).⁵ For health-related data, provenance information establishing a link from the donor to the data should be included (cf. Holub et al., 2018). Further, the origin of the dataset should be stated and proper citation must be facilitated (cf. Go Fair). Poorly described and formatted metadata could negatively affect the re-usability of a dataset (cf. Hu et al., 2017).

As regards SHARE, the re-usability of SHARE data for researchers in general and the SHARE biomarker and accelerometer data are not restricted, except for commercial use. Archiving the data together with a detailed documentation of the (meta)data permits re-use of the data without any time restrictions. Data quality assurance processes of SHARE data are described and published with each wave's release in the

⁵ For an application-oriented guideline on documentation and metadata, see chapter 2 in CESSDA Training Team, 2017-2020.

Methodology Volume series and the Compliance Profiles by SHARE-ERIC⁶. This includes, for instance, reports on fieldwork monitoring, sampling, interviewer training procedures, and innovations such as the implementation of the DBS and accelerometer data collections. Schmidutz and Weiss (2017), e.g., documented the legal, ethical and organisational aspects of the inclusion of DBS in SHARE.

In the attempt to facilitate the re-use of the data derived from DBS, additional steps need to be taken. Laboratory results from DBS samples assays cannot be directly compared to the results from standard assays of 'gold standard' venous blood spots (VBS) even if created under standardised laboratory conditions. Moreover, varying fieldwork conditions and sample quality add further variance to the biomarker levels measured in field-collected DBS samples. In order to allow researchers of the SSH community to easily re-use the DBS data, it is therefore important to compute a conversion formula, which translates the DBS values obtained under fieldwork conditions into gold standard VBS values (cf. A. Börsch-Supan et al., forthcoming; Weiss & Börsch-Supan, 2019).

Data re-use of SHARE data is also increased by providing generated modules (e.g. imputations, weights, ISCED-codes), additionally generated datasets (job episodes panel) and a teaching dataset for student training and for researchers who have little experience in quantitative analyses of complex survey data. Data stemming from the accelerometer project will be made available as such a generated module, which contains aggregated measures that are easy to re-use. Further, more detailed options of making accessible the data from the accelerometer project, e.g., in form of a separate dataset with non-aggregated accelerometer data will be evaluated within the SSHOC project.

⁶ SHARE Methodology Volumes and Compliance Profiles can be accessed via the SHARE homepage: <http://www.share-project.org/data-documentation/methodology-volumes.html> [access 22.03.2021]

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the enhancement of SHARE survey data with biomarker and accelerometer data brought new opportunities, while also demanding new considerations. From an ethical point of view, the principle of 'do not harm' needed to be extended beyond violation of confidentiality to include physical harm such as temporary discomfort or pain. Regarding this, interviewers were provided with adequate additional training. The concepts of informed consent and protection of anonymity and confidentiality were reviewed and adapted adequately whenever necessary to include the new health data.

In general, regarding such projects, a review by an ethics committee is recommended and legally required in some countries, in order to ensure the appropriateness of the practical implementation of the ethics standards and principles as well as data protection measures within a research project. This, in particular, is the case when the data collection includes the collection of human cells or tissues. Researchers need to obtain the approval of a responsible ethics committee, which attest that the overall research project and its procedures, the measures to assure confidentiality and data privacy, and the information given to the participants satisfy international ethical standards.

In general, findability of data for both humans and computer systems is assured by assigning data and associated metadata an abiding, unique identifier and registering it in a comprehensible resource. Using the example of SHARE, its biomarker and accelerometer data collected is permanently identifiable and locatable with to DOIs. All SHARE data is registered in the repository of da|ra, which links every DOI to a set of metadata, a collection of bibliographical and content information, referring to the registered dataset.

In general, data should be accessible and retrievable by their identifier in the long term. Special provisions apply to sensitive and health-related data, which cannot be released via open access because of ethical and legal constraints.

For interoperability and to facilitate merging of data, datasets should be ready to be exchanged, interpreted and combined in a (semi)automated way by humans as well as computer systems. E.g., SHARE data is made available to the research community for two of the most common statistical software packages Stata and SPSS, which can also be accessed using a variety of other statistical analysis tools. The standards and vocabularies used allow interdisciplinary interoperability. The SHARE (meta)data is comprehensively documented, based on DDI standards, to enable researchers from all disciplines to use it for their research and combine it with other datasets.

Lastly, the re-usability of data is an important requirement for the replication and validation of previous research findings as well as for the promotion of scientific knowledge. In order to be re-usable, scientists and computer systems have to be able to assess whether the data is appropriate for the attempted research, hence needing data and metadata to be sufficiently well-described. Taking up again the example of SHARE, DBS and accelerometer data is archived together with a detailed documentation of

the (meta)data to permit the re-use of the data without any time restrictions. Moreover, data quality assurance processes of SHARE data are described and published with each wave's release, including reports on fieldwork monitoring, sampling, interviewer training procedures, and innovations such as the implementation of the DBS and accelerometer data collections but also the documentation of the legal, ethical and organisational aspects of the inclusion of DBS in SHARE. Data re-use of SHARE data is also increased by providing generated modules – which will be made available for the accelerometer data – additionally generated datasets and a teaching dataset.

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